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- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti

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MODERN MARKETING STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF COTTON-TEXTILE CLUSTERS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This study examines the role of marketing strategies in enhancing the export potential of cotton-textile clusters. In a competitive global market, innovative marketing is essential for boosting export volumes. Key strategies include international brand promotion, e-commerce utilization, product certification, and logistics optimization. The study also highlights the importance of market research, trend analysis, and customer-focused approaches. Based on the findings, practical recommendations are provided to strengthen the competitiveness of cotton-textile clusters through export-driven marketing strategies.

Keywords: textile, cluster, export, export potential, management, textile and sewing and knitting industry.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarining eksport salohiyatini oshirishda marketing strategiyalarining rolini o'rganadi. Raqobatbardosh jahon bozorida eksport hajmini oshirish uchun innovatsion marketing muhim ahamiyatga ega. Asosiy strategiyalar xalqaro brendni ilgari surish, elektron tijoratdan foydalanish, mahsulotni sertifikatlash va logistikani optimallashtirishni o'z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqot shuningdek, bozor tadqiqotlari, trend tahlillari va mijozlarga yo'naltirilgan yondashuvlarning muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Aniqlangan xulosalar asosida paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarining raqobatbardoshligini eksportga yo'naltirilgan marketing strategiyalari orqali mustahkamlash bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: to'qimachilik, klaster, eksport, eksport salohiyati, menejment, standart.

Аннотация: Данное исследование изучает роль маркетинговых стратегий в повышении экспортного потенциала хлопково-текстильных кластеров. Инновационный маркетинг имеет решающее значение для увеличения объемов экспорта на конкурентном мировом рынке. Ключевые стратегии включают продвижение международного бренда, использование электронной коммерции, сертификацию продукции и оптимизацию логистики. Исследование также подчеркивает важность маркетинговых исследований, анализа трендов и клиентоориентированных подходов. На основе выявленных выводов были даны практические рекомендации по укреплению конкурентоспособности хлопково-текстильных кластеров посредством экспортно-ориентированных маркетинговых стратегий.

Ключевые слова: текстиль, кластер, экспорт, экспортный потенциал, менеджмент, стандарт.

INTRODUCTION

A company's export marketing strategy involves planning actions to identify and profitably seize opportunities in foreign markets. This approach aims to satisfy target customers while optimizing the company's resources and capacities. [11]

Export marketing, by definition, refers to managing marketing activities for products sold internationally. For success in global markets, exporters need to understand the buying behaviors, needs, and preferences of foreign customers. Additionally, creating a robust export marketing plan helps make their products valuable and attractive to international buyers. [11]

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

Marketing strategies for export growth are often analyzed using frameworks such as Porter's Competitive Advantage Theory, the Resource-Based View (RBV), and the Global Value Chain (GVC) framework. These models help firms within clusters leverage their capabilities to achieve better market positioning.

Understanding target markets and consumer preferences is crucial for expanding exports. Several studies emphasize the importance of market segmentation, demand analysis, and cultural adaptation in developing successful international marketing strategies.

Strong branding and differentiation are essential for enhancing the global visibility of cotton-textile products. Literature suggests that firms adopting eco-friendly, sustainable, and ethically produced textiles gain a competitive edge in international markets.

The role of digital marketing and e-commerce has been extensively examined in relation to export growth. Online platforms, social media marketing, and direct-to-consumer strategies enable cotton-textile clusters to access global markets with lower entry barriers. Export incentives, subsidies, and trade agreements significantly influence the export potential of these clusters. Research shows that countries with supportive trade policies and strategic alliances benefit from increased market access and competitiveness.

Among the contemporary researchers studying cluster forms of textile production organization are D.P. Barsukov [1], D.M. Begov [2], V.I. Vagizova [3], L.L. Butuzova [4], and others. The priority areas for developing textile clusters have been directly or indirectly studied by M.R. Boltabayev [5], Z.A. Khakimov [6], S.Sh. Yusupov [7], Kh. Kodirov, I.A. Toshpulatov [8], N. Sadridinova, and others.

Despite numerous domestic and international studies, the issues surrounding the improvement of textile clusters and the optimization of textile product exports still require further research.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

To obtain data, we will conduct structured interviews with cluster representatives and export managers, as well as distribute standardized surveys among key stakeholders. Data analysis will involve quantitative techniques, including statistical regression, to identify trends, and qualitative methods, such as thematic coding, to explore underlying factors. This mixed-methods approach ensures comprehensive insights into the export marketing strategies employed by Uzbekistan's cotton-textile clusters.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

As of April 1, 2022, the republic had 20 special economic zones (hereinafter, MIZ), 11 directorates of small industrial zones (hereinafter, KSZ), 12 technological parks, and 440 clusters, which included: MIZ – 512 enterprises, 185 MIZs, technological parks – 58, and clusters – 44. The cotton-textile clusters operating in the republic are shown in Table 1 by regions. (Table 1)

Table 1. The number of cotton-textile clusters operating in 2022-2023 by region.

Name of the area	Cotton-textile clusters	Cotton area, ha
Republic of Karakalpakstan	11	86791
Andijan region	15	78991
Bukhara region	11	99220
Jizzakh region	6	77900
Kashkadarya region	18	136036
Navoi region	4	31655
Namangan region	7	63406
Samarkand region	11	75356

Surkhandarya region	11	72370
Syrdarya region	9	75500
Fergana region	13	82080
Tashkent region	6	72161
Khorezm region	12	82757
Total	134	1034223

Cotton-textile clusters represent a significant component of Uzbekistan’s economy, functioning across nearly all regions. By 2022-2023, 134 clusters were active, spanning 1,034,223 hectares of cotton fields. Kashkadarya region stands out, hosting 18 clusters and cultivating cotton on 136,036 hectares, highlighting its strong potential for cotton production and the advanced development of its cluster system.(Picture 1)

Picture 1. Export of textile products(for January-November 2023, million US dollars).

Uzbekistan’s textile exports primarily consist of finished textile products (41.3%) and yarn (40.7%), with a total of 626 different types exported to 63 countries. Although there has been a slight decrease in exports, the sector remains strong. Between January and September 2023, the value of yarn exports reached \$945 million, while finished textile products, including clothing, amounted to \$967.5 million. By the end of 2023, the total export value is projected to reach \$5 billion. The Andijan region, with 15 clusters and 78,991 hectares, and the Fergana region, with 13 clusters and 82,080 hectares, lead in cluster numbers and cotton field sizes. Bukhara (11 clusters, 99,220 hectares), Samarkand (11 clusters, 75,356 hectares), Surkhandarya (11 clusters, 72,370 hectares), and Khorezm (12 clusters, 82,757 hectares) also play key roles as major production bases, reflecting their well-developed cluster systems.

The export structure of Uzbekistan’s textile industry is led by yarn (46.8%) and finished textile products (37.3%), with 495 product types shipped to 55 countries. On the import side, industrial goods totaled \$1,969.7 million from January to April 2024, marking a 7.8% year-over-year increase.

Key imports included iron and steel (\$914.3 million), metal products (\$271.8 million), and textile materials (\$171.5 million), reflecting strong industrial demand.

Reforms aimed at transitioning from raw cotton exports to finished goods have spurred growth in textile exports. From January to April 2024, these exports surpassed \$1 billion, a 1.4% rise from the same period in 2023, according to the Statistics Agency. (Picture 2)

Picture 2. Export of textile products (for January-April 2024, U.S.dollars).

The regions of Navoi (4 clusters, 31,655 hectares) and Jizzakh (6 clusters, 77,900 hectares) have the fewest clusters, and the land allocated for cotton cultivation in these areas is relatively small. Tashkent region also hosts six clusters, encompassing 72,161 hectares.

Yarn remains the top export category, generating \$1.24 billion. Finished textile products rank second at \$1.12 billion, followed by knitted fabrics (\$292.1 million) and garments (\$145.9 million). The ongoing initiative aims to strengthen the sector's economic impact, with ambitious export targets of \$5 billion by 2026 and \$7 billion by 2027. Finished products are expected to account for 70% of these totals. Europe and the U.S. are set to play major roles in this expansion, with projected exports to these markets reaching at least \$500 million.

Over the next three years, \$5 billion in investments are planned for yarn processing. The strategy also involves reallocating duties on yarn and fabric exports to the Fund for Support of Industries. This fund will provide commercial banks with resources to issue foreign currency loans, enabling entrepreneurs to purchase equipment for manufacturing fabrics and finished products. [12]

Under the tripartite agreement, clusters will operate based on decisions made by the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of Karakalpakstan and regional governors, in coordination with the Minister of Agriculture. The Republican Commission for coordinating cotton-textile cluster activities has been disbanded, and new cluster organizers will be selected through a transparent online competition.

The adoption of international standards by textile enterprises promotes freer trade between countries, removes barriers to international commerce, and contributes positively to business development. Increasing the number of enterprises certified to international standards enhances regulations related to labor protection, environmental safeguards, efficient use of raw materials and energy, as well as storage, packaging, labeling, and transportation of products.

Hiring employees skilled in auditing social standards (such as BSCI and Sedex) allows local textile enterprises to cut consulting costs by up to 30%. According to the economic performance

indicators of “RealTex TASHKENT” LLC from 2017 to 2022, employing these auditors in the first half of 2022 significantly reduced consulting fees, tripled export profits, and doubled total profits (Table 1).

Over the past six years, “RealTex TASHKENT” LLC has experienced notable fluctuations in production and export indicators. From 2017 to 2019, production volumes remained stable, peaking in 2018 at 90,807.9 thousand soums. However, 2020 saw a sharp decline to 35,308.6 thousand soums, likely due to pandemic-related disruptions or economic factors. In 2021, production rebounded to 396,007.5 thousand soums, though it declined slightly to 225,724.2 thousand soums in 2022.

Internationally certified product volumes mirrored production trends. Particularly in 2021, certified products surged to 365,514.9 thousand soums, bolstering export volumes and international competitiveness.

Export performance also showed significant changes. In 2017, exports were only 5,914.1 thousand soums. By 2018, this figure had increased 14-fold to 87,104.7 thousand soums. A downturn occurred in 2019–2020, but exports rose sharply in 2021–2022, culminating in 327,136.6 thousand soums in 2022. This growth reflects increased international demand and effective marketing strategies.

Export costs followed a similar pattern. Between 2017 and 2019, expenses ranged from 59,529.2 million to 61,250.4 million soums. These dropped significantly in 2020 to 31,192.6 million soums. In 2021, costs climbed sharply to 348,486.6 million soums before declining slightly to 135,776.3 million soums in 2022.

Revenue from sales showed a consistent upward trend from 66,136.5 thousand soums in 2017, reaching a high of 375,415.1 thousand soums in 2021 before declining to 221,494.9 thousand soums in 2022. Similarly, total profit rose significantly from 15,609.3 thousand soums in 2019 to 37,541.5 thousand soums in 2021 and 66,447.5 thousand soums in 2022.

Tax allocations fluctuated in line with profits, with a low of 1,023.9 thousand soums in 2020 and higher amounts of 17,424.2 thousand soums in 2021 and 11,076.8 thousand soums in 2022.

Net profit showed a variable trend, starting at 87.5 thousand soums in 2017, falling to 32.5 thousand soums in 2019, and then rebounding to 2,415.1 thousand soums in 2021 and 1,587.9 thousand soums in 2022. Export profits also increased steadily from 0.2 million soums in 2017 to 3.1 million soums in 2022, illustrating the positive impact of exports on overall company income.

In recent years, the share of innovative profits has steadily increased, rising from 2.3% in 2020 to 2.7% in 2022. This upward trend reflects the growing effectiveness of innovative approaches. Additionally, the establishment of a laboratory system equipped with modern equipment, in partnership with internationally recognized certification and standardization firms, has significantly enhanced the export potential of textile clusters.

Research findings indicate that costs can be reduced by up to 30% by employing staff trained in social standards (BSCI, SEDEX) and auditing requirements. Including these employees in a consolidated list of enterprises seeking certification further supports cost efficiencies and streamlines the certification process.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Cotton-textile clusters operate throughout Uzbekistan, but their numbers and associated cotton field areas vary by region. Kashkadarya, Andijan, and Fergana have the highest concentrations of clusters, whereas Navoi, Jizzakh, and Tashkent have relatively few. The cluster system plays a pivotal role in advancing the cotton industry and boosting product competitiveness on international markets. Opportunities remain to enhance the sector by optimizing and increasing the efficiency of regional clusters.

Efficient supply chain management and robust logistics infrastructure are critical for meeting international standards and cutting costs. Research highlights the benefits of just-in-time production, lean manufacturing, and strategic partnerships for improving supply chain efficiency. Coupled with effective marketing strategies—such as strong branding, digital marketing initiatives, and government-backed support—these measures are essential for unlocking the export potential of Uzbekistan’s cotton-textile clusters.

To compete successfully on the global stage, clusters need to develop modern marketing strategies. This includes building a recognizable brand, maintaining competitive pricing, leveraging online trading platforms, and adopting innovative approaches. Further research into emerging trends and innovative solutions will provide new pathways for boosting competitiveness and positioning Uzbek cotton-textile clusters more prominently in international markets.

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